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Noble Leadership in The Conquest of Kashmir: Maharaja Ranjit Singh's Era

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Ram Singh Gurna

Supervisor
History
Desh Bhagat University
Mandi Gobindgarh,
Punjab, India

Paramjeet Sidhu

Research Scholar
History
Desh Bhagat University
Mandi Gobindgarh,
Punjab, India

Abstract

In 1799, a process of unification was started by Maharaja Ranjit Singh virtually to establish an empire during the first quarter of the nineteenth century. The occupation of Lahore by Maharaja Ranjit Singh marked a watershed in his career and in the history of Punjab. In the first ten years of this carrier he subverted more than twenty principalities in the plain. Before Maharaja Ranjit Singh signed the treaty of Amritsar with the British in 1809, he was ruling over large areas in all the five Doab's of the Punjab. By the treaty 1809, the British recognized Maharaja Ranjit Singh as the role of sovereign rule of the Punjab and left him free to round off his conquests in the former Mughal province of Lahore. By conquering the north-west Maharaja Ranjit Singh could expand his empire increase his influence and gain access to new resources and trade routes to oust the Afghans from Multan and Kashmir and finally the turn the tables against the successors of Ahmad Shah Abdali in the former Mughal provinces of Kabul. So, Maharaja Ranjit Singh armed to protect his empire from foreign invaders and establish a stable border.

Keywords Unification, Watershed, Subverted, Sovereign, Influence, Stable.

Introduction

Majaraja Ranjit Singh created a vast kingdom with the help of his nobility. At the time of the Maharaja's death, the area of his kingdom had been estimated to be more than one hundred and forty thousand square miles. The composite and numerical strength of the nobility was relative to the expansion and consolidation of the kingdom of Lahore. The expansion of the boundaries required a large reservoir of human resources to manage and administer different regions of the kingdom.

All his nobles contributed a lot for the expansion and consolidation of his kingdom. Recruitment and maintenance of a fixed number of men by the jagirdar was the most important condition of a military jagir. Periodical inspection of the jagirdari troops was necessary to ensure the maintenance of the stipulated number and there are frequent references in contemporary records to the master of troops. They sincerely served a contributed towards the expansion and consolidation. One of the important features of Maharaja Ranjit Singh Kingdom was their occupying the key positions were Jamwal brothers, khatris, Sikhs, Europeons, Bukhara brothers and Kashmir Pandits.

Objective of study

1. To study the interest of Maharaja Ranjit Singh in Kashmir.
2. To explore the role of nobles in winning Kashmir under Lahore Kingdom.
3. To examine the benefits of Kashmir after capturing.

Review of Literature

Cunningham, Joseph Davey (1849), "A History of the Sikhs." This book introduces knowledge about the battles and campaigns of the Lahore Darbar and also deals with the social and economic lives of the nobles during this empire. This book also describes the personalities of the nobles and the court of Lahore. This source is very valuable, so today the scholars read and studied it.

Hugel, Baron Charles (1984), "Kashmir under Maharaja Ranjit Singh (ed) J.S Sharma", this book sheds ample light on detailed description of the culture, religion, and political condition of the Kashmir. In this book, he also presents the fact that he was able to meet with the nobles and gain an understanding of the complex power dynamics that existed during the Lahore kingdom.

Main Text

**"Kashmir, the land of shawls, snow and sun,
Was being eaten by Afghans like a bun"**

Kashmir is a land of delight for outsiders and for them it is a paradise. They enjoy wandering in it. They are enraptured with it. The seduction lies purely in its natural beauty. For its inhabitants it presented a different picture altogether in medieval times. Kashmir is the most beautiful part of India. The enchanting scenery, captivating valleys at a height of over 5,000 feet above sea level, high snow-covered glorious mountains, magnificent lakes and rivers, salubrious climate, charming flowers and delicious fruits have made it one of the most blessed spots on earth. Kashmir was part of the Durrani Kingdom. The situation was that when Shah Shuja's wife, Wafa Begum, approached Diwan Mohkam Chand and Faqir Aziz-ud-din, told them that she would present Maharaja Ranjit Singh with the famous Koh-i-Nur, if he rescued her husband from Kashmir, who was kept a prisoner by the governor of Kashmir for more than a year. Meanwhile, Wazir Fatah Khan of Kabul also made plan to attack Kashmir because he wanted to expel Ata Muhammad Khan from Kashmir for the following reasons:-

1. He had helped Shah Shuja-ul-Mulk in capturing Peshawar in 1810.
2. He had paid no tribute of Kabul.
3. He owed no allegiance to Wazir Fatah Khan.
4. Kashmir was the richest province under Kabul. The Wazir wished to seize the accumulated treasure of the Governor, and to bring the province under his control.

Fatah Khan wanted Maharaja Ranjit Singh's help in his campaign against Kashmir, and sent his trusted agent, Godar Mal to his court. Godar Mal brought with him costly presents and conveyed his master's message to Maharaja Ranjit Singh. If Maharaja sent about twelve thousand troops under Diwan Mohkam Chand, on the condition of receiving as his share one-third of the plunder of the valley. Both offers were good, and the undertakings did not clash with each other. So Maharaja Ranjit Singh accepted the offers and agreed to the undertakings. Maharaja Ranjit Singh and wazir Fateh Khan met in December 1812, at Rohtas on the western bank of the Jehlum. Maharaja Ranjit Singh proposed that the two armies should proceed by the Mirpur and Rajauri route instead of the Muzaffarabad route, as the latter, he thought, must be under snow at that time and they were agreed upon. Diwan Mohkam Chand and Sardar Dal Singh were put in command of the Durbar forces and Maharaja Ranjit Singh gave them strict instructions that Shah Shuja must be liberated and secured at any cost.

Diwan Mohkam Chand and Sardar Dal Singh marched with Fateh Khan, the combined forces crossed the Jehlam, but the Afghan had no intention of allowing the Sikhs any large share either in the conquest or in its results and had only carried on negotiations to secure the Maharaja's neutrality. No sooner had the force reached Pir Panjal than he, without consulting Diwan Mohkam Chand or informing him of his intention, pressed on by double marches with his hardly mountain troops, while the Sikhs, never of much use in the hills, were unable to move owing to a heavy fall of snow. The Diwan saw the design of Fateh Khan but he was not disconcerted. He promised the Rajaori chief a Jagir of Rs 25,000. If he would show him a pass by which he might reach the valley at the same time as Fateh Khan, which he contrived to do with a handful of troops under Sardar Jodh Singh Kalsia and Sardar Nihal Singh Attariwala. The Diwan was thus present at the capture of Shergarh and Hari Parbat and the reduction of the valley, which was a work of no difficulty, for Atta Muhammad the Governor had fled and little resistance was offered; but his force was too weak to be of much assistance and Fateh Khan declared that the Sikhs were not entitled to their share of the spoil. When Maharaja came to know that Wazir Fateh Khan refused to share the plunder, he was determined to revenge. In the first Kashmir expedition, Diwan Mohkam Chand got Shah Shuja and also acquainted himself with the geography of the area that helped him in guiding the Khalsa army on their future course.

In 1814, Maharaja made full preparations for the second expedition of Kashmir. Diwan Mohkam Chand, who during the first expedition had gained considerable experience about the terrain, openly and sincerely advised the king against it. He put forward strong arguments in support of his views. He emphasized that the season was not suitable for operations in that territory, but the Maharaja would not listen to the ageing Diwan Mohkam Chand and ordered the Diwan's grandson, Ram Dayal, a strapping youth of twenty, to lead the campaign against Kashmir. In the month of June the expeditionary

force reached Rajauri. Maharaja Ranjit Singh himself, as the head of the main army, was marching along the Punch route by the Tosh Maidan pass and a detachment under Diwan Ram Dayal, Sardar Dal Singh and Namdar Khan Thakkar was to march to Haripur and Shupiyon from Bahramgala. Diwan Ram Dayal's detachment secured the Pirpanjal pass, occupied Haripur, but failed in its attack on Shupiyon. The Afghan opposition was stubborn and what was more unfortunate that because of rains the Khalsa guns could not be fired during the battle which followed. In a battle of swords Jiwan Mal Munshi, an ideal dare-devil Khalsa Ghorcharah, and Sardar Fateh Singh Chachi were both killed. Diwan Ram Dayal had consequently to fall back and ask for reinforcements. The main army, under Maharaja Ranjit Singh himself, reached Punch only to find itself exposed to rain and storm. Maharaja Ranjit Singh advanced to Mandi, thence to Tosh Maidan Pass where he found Azim Khan entrenched. He heard here about the distress of Diwan Ram Dayal's detachment and sent Ram Singh, Diwan Devi Das and Kutbuddin with as many soldiers as he could spare to aid the hard-pressed brilliant young grandson of his trusted commander-in-chief. Maharaja Ranjit Singh, with a precarious supply and with insufficient troops, was unable to continue in that position. His retreat was in fact precipitous and attended with very considerable loss. He fell back on Mandi, thence to Punch, continued his retreat, reaching his capital about the middle of August. Amar Nath says, however, that Diwan Ram Dayal killed 2,000 Afghans and forced the Afghan army to retreat. Azim Khan took fright, told Diwan Ram Dayal about his friendship for Diwan Mohkam Chand and sent some presents for the Lahore Kingdom as also a written document admitting its supremacy. Diwan Ram Dayal there upon retired. It is not probable that Diwan Ram Dayal actually won any great victory.

It is also almost a certainty that Azim Khan was not the man to let a Khalsa army slip from his grasp merely out of respect (which, from the nature of the circumstances, might not be very genuine) for the grandfather of the commandant. Therefore, the most likely interpretation is that Diwan Ram Dayal was too strongly entrenched to be defeated or dislodged without great difficulty and a very considerable sacrifice. Diwan Ram Dayal, too, felt very insecure because of the retreat of the main army. Therefore both parties were eager to come to terms and there were talks of Azim Khan's friendship for Diwan Mohkam Chand. The Kashmir expedition brought Maharaja Ranjit Singh only a costly parchment. At Lahore he had a private conference with Diwan Mohkam Chand and Rani Sada Kaur in which he remarked that the province of Kashmir had remained out of his hands simply on account of the troops of Bhai Ram Singh the traitor, that in this expedition lakhs of rupees had been spent and a great deal of disgrace and insult had been incurred by him from the viewpoint of his rivals, of course, Ram Singh's cowardly retreat with the troops under his charge was largely responsible for undermining the morale of the Khalsa army but there was also the brilliant rally under Diwan Ram Dayal as a balancing factor, Diwan Mohkam Chand and Rani Sada Kaur replied, 'It was very unfortunate that the noble Sarkar did not accept their earlier suggestion'. The whole expedition returned to Lahore, having lost its best officers and men, and being shorn of everything that constituted its strength and utility as a military body. The Maharaja lamented that in the campaign he could not avail himself of his aged Diwan's determination and judgement, as well as of his skill and valour. Everything had come to pass exactly as the old Diwan had predicted and the ruler of Lahore sighed at the political blunder he had committed. Thus the Maharaja valued and appreciated Diwan Mohkam Chand's skill and bravery.

In April, 1819 Maharaja Ranjit Singh took council how he might conquer Kashmir. At this time, Kashmir was ruled by Jabar Khan, on behalf of his brother Azim Khan who had lately departed to establish himself at Peshawar. Another favorable circumstance arose from the arrival of one Bir Dhar, the able minister of the governor of Kashmir, at the Sikh court, where he had found refuge after falling out with his master. He supplied much useful information to the Maharaja concerning the strength and disposition of the Afghan army, and various routes to Kashmir. A large expeditionary force was organized and divided into three sections. For the conquest of Kashmir on 1819, the Maharaja marched from Lahore at the head of 30,000 strong force. The force marched with shouts Sat-Sri-Akal resounding in the sky. A large army was collected at Wazirabad which was divided into three columns. The first was led by Misr Diwan Chand including sardar Hukma Singh Chimni, Sardar Jawala Singh and Sardar Sham Singh Attariwala. While the Prince Kharak Singh headed a supporting column along with Sardar Hari Singh Nalwa and Maharaja Ranjit Singh himself remained behind with a reserve and for the purpose of expediting the transit of the various munitions of war. The advance column started from Bhimber in May, an opportune season for moving to Kashmir, and reached Rajauri in a few days. The Diwan carried with him only light mountain guns. At the end of June he reached Bahram Gala and secured the passage to the Pir-Panjal.

Misr Diwan Chand divided the army under him into three directions, each of which was to reach the valley by a different route. He himself headed the detachment which had to cross the Pir-Panjal, and crossed this barrier, descended into the valley. The Afghans opposed this advanced detachment, and an engagement ensued, which lasted the whole

day. Many were killed on both sides, till, at length, the Sikh charging with the bayonet, the Afghans fled in dismay, leaving their camp, which was plundered. On the 16th June, the entire Khalsa force, some twelve thousands strong-collected together near Supin. Jabar Khan was also entrenched there at the head of five thousand men. The Sikh attacked him. The Afghans at first defended themselves heroically, repulsed the invaders and captured two of their guns. But the latter retrieved their position by a determined attack, and the Afghans had to give way to superior numbers and discipline. They fled in disorder. Both sides lost heavily. Jabar Khan himself was among the wounded. The valley was thus secured by the Sikhs, who made a triumphant entry into Srinagar. On entering city, the soldiers began to plunder but were energetically stopped by the Misr Diwan Chand.

After capturing Kashmir Maharaja Ranjit Singh very much impressed by Misr Diwan Chand's efforts in Kashmir battle. So, he was given the title of Fateh-o-nusrat.

Conclusion Thus, the victory of Kashmir added a feather in Maharaja Ranjit Singh's turban. The fertile and picturesque valley was not only a financial asset, but it also extended the frontiers of his state to China and Tibet. It also added to the revenue of the Lahore Darbar as well. Srinagar besides being a centre of flourishing shawl making industry, was the hub of trade between Punjab, Ladakh, Skardu and Tibet. The Maharaja now sent Faqir Aziz-ud-Din to make a detailed report on the conquered province and appointed Moti Ram, the son of Diwan Mohkam Chand as the first Governor. The chiefs of several principalities connected with Kashmir, accepted the suzerainty of the Maharaja on their own; others were subjugated by the Governor of Kashmir.

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